

A Review on the Drip Irrigation System of Greenhouse Crops in Cambodia

Chea Mengponleu^{1*}, Serey Mardy²

¹National University of Battambang, Graduate School, ²Svay Rieng University, Faculty of Agriculture

Corresponding Author: Chea Mengponleu cheaponleu16@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Drip Irrigation System, Greenhouse, Water Use Efficiency, Fertilization, Evapotranspiration

Received : 02, August

Revised : 14, August

Accepted: 17, September

©2023 Chea Mengponleu, Serey Mardy:

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

Drip irrigation systems have been providing efficient water in the dry season in Cambodia. In Agriculture 4.0, MAFF signed MoU with a private company to build 10,000 greenhouses to supply 400 tons of crops annually. The objective of this review paper is to synthesize the literature on drip irrigation of greenhouse crops and the benefits of drip irrigation in greenhouses. Drip irrigation can be applied to reduce the impact of drought and climate change on food production; to remedy groundwater and rivers contamination caused by fertilizer leaching; and to support the livelihoods of rural communities. Moreover, it has the highest water efficiency in the dry season. In greenhouses, water and fertilizer usage efficiency is improved in the rainy seasons by using plastic covers on the roof. Therefore, Agriculture 4.0, combined with drip irrigation and greenhouses, helps farmers grow crops throughout the year. Farmers' knowledge should be upgraded in using, maintaining, and repairing both drip irrigation systems and greenhouses.

INTRODUCTION

Technology that supports specialized farming methods aiming at greater efficiency and less environmental impact is referred to as "precision agriculture." (Kittas et al., 2014). Drip irrigation is one of the most effective method of nutrient and water delivering to crops. The plant receives the exact amount of water and nutrients required for optimum growth by being watered straight to its root zone (Netafirm, 2015). With the MoU, all parties must collaborate to erect 10,000 Agriculture 4.0 greenhouses over the course of the following ten years, each of which must be capable of producing at least 400 tons of crops annually. Greenhouse cooperation and Agriculture 4.0: changing farmers into agnoproteins (Sivutha, 2022). The goal of irrigation management is frequently to maintain soil or substrate water content in close approximation to field capacity while ensuring maximum water delivery for plant growth and yield (Bacci et al., 2011). Efficient use and management of water on crops as the amount of water needed for agriculture tends to increase (MAFF, 2022).

The majority of agriculture in Cambodia is rainfed, and it is weather-dependent and susceptible to risks from climate change because of its modest inputs, moderately fertile or deficient soils, low to moderate yields, and poor productivity (Monin, 2021). Floods and droughts recur frequently in Cambodia as a result of an excess of water during the rainy season and a deficiency during the dry season. These extremes have harmed human lives, crops, homes, and infrastructure (Sithirith, 2021).

This review contains published material about drip irrigation and greenhouses. However, most of the available research on drip irrigation in general will apply to greenhouses. To enumerate advantages or disclose relevant information that is not generally available, additional literature has been incorporated. Additionally, this review includes published literature on the advantages and limitations of drip irrigation and greenhouses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The dry season is running from the mid-November to early April, and Cambodia has a tropical climate. The dry season may be separated into two distinct periods: the first, from mid-February to May, is the coolest time of year, while the second, from mid-March to June (World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal, 2021).

The term "drip irrigation," as it is more widely known, is accurate. Water is delivered to plant roots one drop at a time. If used appropriately, this kind of irrigation might be the most water-efficient one, as evaporation and runoff are reduced. Drip irrigation and plastic mulch are frequently used in contemporary agriculture to further reduce evaporation and distribute nutrients (Megersa & Abdulahi, 2015). In particular, in water-limited regions, the quantity of applied water (and its cost) plays a significant role in the financial viability of irrigated field crops (Segoli, 2018).

The components of a conventional drip irrigation system are as follows: the pump unit extracts water from the source and pumps it into the pipe network at the correct pressure. The valves that make up the control head control the pressure and discharge across the entire system. Mainlines, sub-

domains, and laterals dispense water into the fields from the control head. Emitters, or drippers, are equipment for managing the water's flow from the lateral to the plants.

A drip irrigation system design tool that uses continuous watering and water absorption to evaluate the impact of geometrical characteristics on water consumption effectiveness. Instead of the hydraulics of the irrigation system (pump, valve, filter, pipe diameters, etc.), design refers to the geometrical features of the drip irrigation system. The distances between underground emitters and between drip lines, the size and depth of root systems, and the distances between emitters along drip lines are a few examples. Considering the water application schedule in place and the diurnal pattern of the plant-atmosphere water-absorption resistance, the technique of optimising drip irrigation schedules for both intermittent irrigation (every few days) and continuous irrigation pulses is referred to as "scheduling" (Friedman et al., 2018).

METHODOLOGY

This study is a literature research article. A qualitative approach combined with a descriptive analytic method is the methodology employed. The data is derived from journal articles, books, policies/regulations, reports, and news from online media. Data collection methods include finding, obtaining, and studying the aforementioned written materials. Online media websites, reputable institution websites, research database websites, reading books or e-books, and online media websites are all used for data searching. The data analysis technique is done through some steps, which are data organizing, reading (taking notes), describing, clarifying, and drawing conclusions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Benefit of Irrigation System

Drip irrigation is to water into the soil at very low rates (2-20 liters/hour) using a system of small diameter plastic pipes equipped with outlets known as emitters or drippers. Drip irrigation is sometimes referred to as trickling irrigation. By using drip irrigation, we can lessen the effects of drought and climate change on food production, prevent fertilizer leaching from contaminating groundwater and rivers, help rural communities, fight poverty, and stem urban migration (Netafim, 2022).

Farmers

Drip irrigation not only provides a higher return on investment (ROI) than other irrigation technologies, but it also provides farmers with an effective and straightforward approach to running their farms. Farmers profit from drip irrigation because it ensures greater, consistent-quality harvests and considerable water savings. Drip irrigation reliably irrigates in every topography and soil type with zero evaporation, zero runoff, zero waste, and 100 percent land use. It saves energy since it operates with low water pressure.

With less leaching, less reliance on the weather, greater stability, and less risks, effective fertilizer and crop protection (Netafim, 2022; Narayanamoorthy, 2005).

Plants

Drip irrigation maintains perfect growth conditions and aids in producing the highest-possible crops by often and sparingly applying water and nutrients. Drip irrigation is also used in contemporary agriculture to supply fertilizer. Drip irrigation increases plant productivity. High availability of water and nutrients; water and nutrient dosages adjusted to the plant's growth requirements; proper soil aeration and lack of saturation; absence of high salinity brought on by excessive fertilizer application; absence of leaf wetness, which can lead to fungus infections (Netafim, 2022; Shoji, 1977).

Greenhouse Crops

Irrigation scheduling should be managed to (i) supply plants with a volume of water equal to the volume of water transpired for maintaining crop productivity, (ii) overcome differences in water discharge, achieving high water uniformity, and (iii) move excessive salts towards the rooting system, avoiding soil salination (Pardossi et al., 2011). Growing in popularity in recent years, greenhouse-based tomato cultivation in Cambodia is thought to reduce the likelihood of crop failure brought on by insect pests, plant diseases, and several abiotic factors (Ro et al., 2021). Although it is not particularly precise, it is recommended to utilize the water balancing approach to solve this issue for soil-based greenhouse systems by keeping track of all water inputs and losses to a field (Snyder, 2014). Farmers must handle a sizable portion of the advancements in greenhouse water and fertilizer usage efficiency (Kitta et al., 2015). With the help of smart technology, greenhouses can now grow crops more quickly, more sustainably, and in nearly any weather (Inbar, 2020).

Open-air agriculture may experience waste, subpar yields, or plant disease as a result of the laborious human procedure, but greenhouses are a different story (Maor, 2020). Under greenhouses, crops are protected from adverse weather conditions like wind, rain, hail, and snow as well as from blights and diseases. On a station-average basis, the yearly rainfall in Cambodia ranges from 1087 to 1528 mm. The pre-monsoon season sees around 5-20% of the yearly rainfall, the summer monsoon season sees 50-78%, and the post-monsoon season sees 12-36% (Tsujiimoto et al., 2018). Temperature, global sun radiation, precipitation, and wind strength are the four primary climatic factors that have the biggest effects on the architecture of the building and the caliber of the interior microclimate. Consequently, the structural design of greenhouses as well as the inside climate control equipment are both significantly influenced by local climatic conditions (Von Elsner et al., 2000). For healthy plant development and maximum output, greenhouses need to offer the ideal climate. Along with the mechanical operation of the greenhouse structure, the design has a significant impact on internal climatic variables, including temperature, air, humidity, and light transmission.

CONCLUSION

This study reviews drip irrigation systems used in greenhouse crop production. The soil, substrate, and crop features of the greenhouse environment should be taken into account when scheduling irrigation to follow the diurnal course of evapotranspiration. Drip irrigation systems are designed to create an intelligent irrigation scheduling system that will allow irrigation farmers to optimize water consumption and only irrigate where and when necessary for as long as necessary during the dry season. Around the world, agriculture's greenhouse business is expanding and becoming increasingly competitive. However, local variables have an impact on greenhouse design, leading to a wide range of greenhouse types that are constructed with various covering materials and tailored to the local environment. Add on, farmers must manage a sizable portion of the improvement in greenhouse fertilizer and water usage efficiency, and to be adopted on drip irrigation and greenhouses, it is a new thing for them and they need the private sector, NGOs, and government support.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "A Review on the Drip Irrigation System of Greenhouse Crops in Cambodia."

REFERENCES

- Bacci, L., Battista, P., Cardarelli, M., Carmassi, G., Roupael, Y., Incrocci, L., Malorgio, F., Pardossi, A., Rapi, B., & Colla, G. (2011). *Modelling evapotranspiration of container crops for irrigation scheduling. Evapotranspiration – From Measurements to Agricultural and Environmental Applications*, Gerosa, G., Ed, 263-282.
- Friedman, S., Gamlielunar, A., & Comm, G. (2018). DIDAS - A User-Friendly Program For Assisting Drip Irrigation Design And Scheduling. IsraelAgri. Retrieved from: http://www.studioappel.com/ebooks/nobel/precision_Irrigation_Nov18/mobile/index.html#p=1
- Inbar, O. (2020). *Greenhouse technology, the future is already here*. In Greenhouse Technology (p. 8). Israelagri.

- Kitta, E., Bartzanas, T., Katsoulas, N., & Kittas, C. (2015). Benchmark irrigated under cover agriculture crops. *Agriculture and agricultural science procedia*, 4, 348-355.
- Kittas, C., Elvanidi, A., Katsoulas, N., Ferentinos, K., & Bartzanas, T. (2014). *Reflectance indices for the detection of water stress in greenhouse tomato (Solanum lycopersicum)*. Paper presented at the XXIX International Horticultural Congress on Horticulture: Sustaining Lives, Livelihoods and Landscapes (IHC2014): 1112.
- MAFF. (2022). Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (HE) Minister Veng Sakhon Leads Private Sector Investing in Cambodian Agriculture to Visit Netafim. Retrieved from: <https://web.maff.gov.kh/newsdetail/2YZdCc3plh?lang=en>
- Maor, T. (2020). *High-Tech Machine learning in the greenhouse? In Greenhouse Technology* (p. 28). Israelagri.
- Megersa, G., & Abdulahi, J. (2015). Irrigation system in Israel: A review. *International Journal of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering*, 7(3).
- Monin, N. (2021). *The Impacts of Climate Change on Agriculture and Water Resources in Cambodia: From Local Communities' Perspectives*. CDRI Working Paper Series.

- Narayanamoorthy, A. (2005). Economics of drip irrigation in sugarcane cultivation: Case study of a farmer from Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 60(2).
- Netafim. (2015). *Drip Irrigation Handbook Understanding the basics*. Retrieved from Drip Irrigation Handbook Understanding the basics: <https://www.netafim.com/en/drip-irrigation/>
- Netafim. (2022). *Drip Irrigation*. Retrieved from: <https://www.netafim.com/en/drip-irrigation/>
- Ro, S., Chea, L., Ngoun, S., Stewart, Z. P., Roeun, S., Theam, P., Lim, S., Sor, R., Kosal, M., & Roeun, M. (2021). Response of tomato genotypes under different high temperatures in field and greenhouse conditions. *Plants*, 10(3), 449.
- Segoli, M. (2018). *Optimizing Irrigation and fertilization using lysimeters, Precision irrigation & water management*. Israelagri: Israel.
- Shoji, K. (1977). In this system plastic pipes laid on the surface of the ground deliver water to plants drop by drop. The system reduces stress on the plant, conserves water and works well with saline water. *SCIENTIFIC AMERICAN*.
- Sithirith, M. (2021). Downstream State and Water Security in the Mekong Region: A Case of Cambodia between Too Much and Too Little Water. *Water*, 13(6), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13060802>

- Sivutha, N. (2022, January 24). Public-private Agriculture 4.0 greenhouse deal struck. *The Phnom Penh Post*. <https://phnompenhpost.com/business/public-private-agriculture-40-greenhouse-deal-struck>
- Snyder, R. L. (2014). *Irrigation scheduling: Water balance method*. University of California, Department of Land, Air and Water Resources Atmospheric Science. Davis: Berkeley, CA, USA, 1-39.
- Pardossi, A., Carmassi, G., Diara, C., Incrocci, L., Maggini, R., & Massa, D. (2011). *Fertigation and substrate management in closed soilless culture*. Pisa: University of Pisa.
- Tsujimoto, K., Ohta, T., Aida, K., Tamakawa, K., & So Im, M. (2018). Diurnal pattern of rainfall in Cambodia: Its regional characteristics and local circulation. *Progress in Earth and Planetary Science*, 5(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-018-0192-7>
- Von Elsner, B., Briassoulis, D., Waaijenberg, D., Mistrionis, A., Von Zabeltitz, C., Gratraud, J., Russo, G., & Suay-Cortes, R. (2000). Review of structural and functional characteristics of greenhouses in European Union countries: Part I, design requirements. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research*, 75(1), 1-16.
- World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal. (2021). *Cambodia, Current Climate, Climatology*. <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/>